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**3RD
INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE
2026**

2026 DRI CONFERENCE

THEME:

**“Contemporary Practices of
Philanthropy in Africa:
Prospects and Challenges”**

ORGANIZED BY:

**Dawood Research
Institute (DRI)**

KEY EVENT/ACTIVITY DATES:

Arrival: Mon. 20th April, 2026 **Opening:** Tue. 21st April, 2026

Sessions: Wed. 22nd April, 2026

Closing and Excursion: Thur. 23rd April, 2026

Departure: Fri. 24th April, 2026

Conference Secretariate:
Dawood Research Institute, Jos
No. 137, Bauchi Road, Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Introduction

The Dawood Research Institute (DRI) is a non-profit research organization registered in Nigeria. DRI conducts its research activities in Nigeria in collaboration with local and international partners. Its main activities are social and academic research and most of these have been in the area of philanthropic studies, interfaith relations, social justice and offering consultancy services. DRI also organizes conferences and workshops aimed at making lasting impact in Nigerian society as well as Africa at large. The 1st international conference organized by DRI in April 2023 was on “Contemporary Practice of *Zakat* in Africa” with funding from the Muslim Philanthropy Initiative, Indiana University, which brought together scholars and practitioners from Nigeria and parts of Africa. The conference was held at the University of Jos, Nigeria. The theme of the 2nd DRI international conference was “Contemporary Practice of Philanthropy and Educational Endowment in Africa” held in February 2024 at the Bayero University Kano in collaboration with Indiana University, USA and six universities in Nigeria. The conference was funded by the Ford Foundation, Habibiyya Islamic Society, and Ammasco International Ltd, Nigeria.

The theme for DRI's 3rd international conference is “Contemporary Practices of Philanthropy in Africa: Prospects and Challenges.” This is meant as a follow-up on development in the area of philanthropy and to draw scholarly attention to this emerging area of study in Africa. Our hope is that this conference will attract wider attention from Nigeria, other countries within Africa and different parts of the world.

Conference Location: Faculty of Arts, University of Abuja, FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) is chosen for this conference because of its strategic position in Nigeria and easy accessibility for both local and international participants.

Collaborations:

Apart from the Muslim Philanthropy Initiative, Lilly Family School of Philanthropy, Indiana University, USA, University of Abuja, and the University of Jos, we are currently discussing collaboration with different partners.

Partnership and Sponsorship:

We are seeking sponsorship from different bodies and individuals for the success of this conference because Abuja is an expensive city. The logos of partners and sponsors will be displayed on the conference banners, will be published in the conference book containing abstracts, and included in all the Institute's social media platforms and other promotional materials.

Participants:

We are expecting both local and international participants at the conference. The category of participants expected to attend this conference in Abuja, Nigeria include:

1. *Scholars:* The conference will bring together scholars from different universities in Nigeria, Africa and other places in the world to share their research and insights on philanthropic practices in Africa.
2. *Practitioners:* The conference will bring together practitioners that are administering organizations, foundations, NGOs, and heading community initiatives that are engaged in philanthropic work in Nigeria and other African countries.
3. *Individual Philanthropists:* The conference is expected to bring together some High-Net-Worth Philanthropists from Nigeria and other African countries to share their experiences and research expectations.
4. *Politicians and Policymakers:* The conference will also bring together politicians and policymakers from different countries in Africa. This category will include dignitaries such as the Vice President of Nigeria in the person of Kashim Shettima Mustapha. Also, government representatives are expected to attend from Nigeria and selected African countries.
5. *Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs):* The conference is also expected to attract a large number of humanitarian NGOs.

Keynote Speakers and Lead Paper Presenters:

The conference CPC has identified two keynote speakers and some Lead Paper presenters as follows:

Keynote Speakers

1. **Prof. Shariq Ahmed Siddiqui** (Director, Muslim Philanthropy

Initiative, Indiana University, USA).

2. **Dr. Kole Shettima** (Director, Nigeria Office, MacArthur Foundation, Abuja).

Lead Paper Presenters:

3. **Dr. Catherine Aniagolu-Okoye (ChiChi)** (Regional Director for West Africa, Ford Foundation, Lagos, Nigeria).
4. **Mr. Arif Ekram** (Senior Manager of Partnerships, Candid, New York, USA).
5. **Dr. Micah Hughes** (Associate Director, Center for Middle East and Islamic Studies, University of North Carolina, USA).
6. **Dr. Steenberg Reyhe Rune** (Principal Investigator, Asian Studies Department, Palacky University Olomouc, Czech Republic).
7. **Dr. Sokfa Francis** (Deputy Director, Centre for Mediation in Africa, University of Pretoria, South Africa).
8. **Prof. Nantawe Goshwe Yilwatda** (Honourable Minister of Humanitarian Affairs, Disaster Management and Social Development, Abuja, Nigeria). **Waiting for confirmation.**
9. **Rt. Hon. Yusuf Adamu Gagdi**, PhD (Member, Representing Pankshin/Kanke/Kanam Federal Constituency, National Assembly, Abuja, Nigeria). **Waiting for confirmation.**

Co-Chairpersons for the Opening Day

1. Alh. Ibrahim Sale Hassan
2. Sheikh Nuruddeen Lemu

Conference Objectives

Specific objectives of the 2026 philanthropy conference include:

1. To explore the current state of philanthropy including challenges and opportunities in different parts of Africa.
2. To foster collaborations and networking between philanthropists, practitioners, researchers, and policymakers in Africa.
3. To showcase innovative philanthropic practices and models in Africa.
4. To create and facilitate an interactive platform that will bring together practitioners and researchers in Africa.
5. To promote the study of philanthropy in Africa.

Overview of the Conference Theme

Philanthropic practices have grown from strength to strength in Africa, which generates a lot of scholarly interest as well as entice the attention of local and international foundations, NGOs, and community initiatives. This has gradually progressed over the last two decades. The recent boost in philanthropic activities in Africa came as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown (2020-2022); foundations, NGOs and particularly individual philanthropists became visible on social media.

This advanced philanthropic practices and activities to another level that have become effective in reducing the agony of people in need. Today, the scene of philanthropy is witnessing diverse interest groups; wealthy individuals, practitioners, foundations and NGOs affiliated to both local and international donor agencies, faith-based and community initiatives, etc. Sub-Saharan Africa is home to numerous complex issues ranging from poverty to health and malnutrition, from inadequate education to lack of sufficient social welfare and limited social justice, as some prominent examples. Therefore, billions of dollars in foreign aid enters Africa annually, which is directed towards humanitarian purposes to alleviate suffering and improve the economic wellbeing and standard of livelihood of those people in need. Local effort is exerted to assist a cross section of vulnerable members of society. This is achieved by those motivated from different primary perspectives: religious and social (humanitarian).

As donors make desperate efforts from various convictions to assist and improve the quality of life of the indigent, diverse practitioners also provide their own contributions by disseminating and channeling funding into different aspects of need. It is assumed that local philanthropists and some organizations, as well as community initiatives, are often closer to the people and that therefore, they are more aware of people's needs. The rise of charitable activities of local philanthropists reflects the fact that they are individually and collectively realizing the importance of giving back to their communities towards the social wellbeing of the society they live in, addressing critical issues such as education, healthcare, daily feeding and shelter. Professionals are scattered in different local and international organizations, some in paid employment while others are providing services

evolving around philanthropy in Africa. The responsibility of scholars is to analyze these philanthropic endeavors and to provide recommendations for the rest of the world to better understand these processes, developments and shortcomings in Africa and to respond with enhanced interventions and superior strategies in the deployment and allocation of resources. Research can also help professionals, foundations and NGOs to understand areas that require more attention.

Therefore, the Dawood Research Institute (DRI), its local and international partners are creating a forum to the facilitation of cutting-edge research, symposiums and a series of international conferences on the different developments pertaining to the current philanthropic landscape in Africa. DRI's publications are also avenues that encourage discourse on philanthropic activities/practices in Africa. This conference will bring together scholars from different universities and institutions in Africa and beyond, professionals and individual philanthropists as well as foundations and NGOs to share their research, experiences and recommendations.

Under the theme of the conference: “Contemporary Practices of Philanthropy in Africa: Prospects and Challenges”, participants are expected to look at philanthropy from a broader perspective considering models of excellent in diverse African societies. Abstracts for participation in this conference can be submitted on any of the following sub-themes (but not limited to them):

- The Impact of Philanthropy on Development in Africa
- Motivation, Opportunities and Challenges of Philanthropy in Africa
- Theoretical and Conceptual Analyses of Philanthropy
- Philanthropy and the Role of Charitable Foundations in Africa
- The Challenges Confronting Philanthropic Institutions and NGOs in Africa
- Philanthropy, Faith-Based Organizations and Development in Africa
- The Rise of Community-Based Philanthropy in Africa
- The Challenges of Collaboration among Philanthropic Institutions in Africa
- Philanthropy, Healthcare, and Educational Development in Africa

- The Field of Philanthropy and Scholarly Publications in Africa
- The Role of Philanthropy in Poverty Alleviation in Africa
- International Donor Organizations, Aid Cut, and Philanthropy in Africa
- Ramadan and Charitable Giving in Africa
- Financial Institutions and Corporate Philanthropy in Africa
- Contesting Philanthropy in Africa: Needy and Professional Beggars
- Crowdfunding and Online Philanthropy in Africa
- The Rise of Female Philanthropists, a Challenge for Male Philanthropists in Africa?
- Philanthropy and Socio-Economic Development in Africa

Participants (especially scholars) are expected to submit abstracts of not more than 150 words for consideration. Full papers are not to exceed 8,000 words, should be 12-point font size, Times New Roman, 1.5 line-space. Both abstracts and full papers must be written in American English. Accepted papers will be informed of the citation format to use.

Language of Presentation:

The language preferences are:

1. Scholars and practitioners will present their papers in English.
2. Individual philanthropists can choose to make presentations in any language of their choice provided there will be a translator.

Registration:

Outside Africa: \$200

From Africa: \$50

From Nigeria: N30,000

NGOs should contact DRI for their conference registration.

